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Barriers and enabling factors for engaging engineering students in research. A multi-perspective approach.

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Abstract

Industry 4.0 requires diverse, creative, and adaptable engineers, who solve complex problems based on innovation, research, and development. Thus, engaging students in research is a potentially high-impact educational practice. However, previous studies have shown that implementing students' engagement in research faces multiple obstacles that stress on the dimensions culture, resources in higher education institutions, structure of study programmes, academics' qualification and students' competencies. In engineering, however, little attention is spent on what academics and students perceive as barriers and enabling factors. This study highlights conditions for engaging students in research in engineering education. For this, we conducted six semi-structured interviews with students and academics at a German university of technology and analyzed those using thematic analysis. We found that interviewees perceive students' engagement in research differently and associate a wide range of activities. Together, they draw a manifold picture of its constraints. Beside common aspects, they identified the large amount of obligatory basic courses and the lack of practice in undergraduate programmes as hindering; a structure quite typical in German traditional engineering education. They also made various recommendations, such as supporting a culture for engaging students in research, appropriate facilities, and programme-based research skill development. Furthermore, they reported that academics need an open mind for topics of students' interest, while students are required to engage in extracurricular student-academic partnerships in research. Upon those findings, we argue for the need for further research and, subsequently, suggest formulating strategies by involving all stakeholders. This can potentially ensure developing future engineering talents at this university and beyond.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Industry 4.0 desires diverse, creative, and adaptable engineers with sound technological skills who contribute to complex problem solving in society (see [1]) based on innovation, research, and development. Thus, engaging students in research is a potentially high-impact educational practice (see [2]), and its benefits in engineering education has been outlined elsewhere (see e.g. [3]). Various activities and strategies can be implemented to integrate research into teaching (e.g. [4], [5]). However, implementing students' engagement in research faces multi-dimensional obstacles and facilitating factors, i.e. regarding culture and policies as well as resources in higher education institutions, the structure of study programmes, academics' qualification and students' competencies, as observed by senior and junior academics (e.g. [6], [7]). Some studies summarized similar challenging and enabling conditions, that is, institutional, departmental and disciplinary conditions as well as course design and personal attributes (e.g. [8]). Brew and Mantai (2017) refer to other studies that stress the relevance of taking into account the various perceptions of research, teaching and learning, definitions, attitudes, actions and benefits of engaging students in research. In addition, disciplinary characteristics (see [4]) and contextual aspects of higher education institutions have to be considered (e.g. [9]). So far however, little attention has been spent on what both academics and students in engineering education perceive as barriers and facilitating factors. Following our first findings (see [7]), this qualitative study, conducted with three stakeholder groups at a German university of technology, discusses how academics and students understand research, teaching, and engaging students in research, what they perceive as barriers and enabling factors, and which ideas they have for enhancing students' engagement in research. Based on these results, a complementary quantitative study, conducted as a university-wide questionnaire, is planned.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

Engaging students in research is framed throughout this manuscript in a wider sense in the framework of the *extended research-teaching-nexus* model according to Rueß et al. (2016), which is based on the approach of Healey (2005). Therein, *research-based learning* in a narrow sense refers to a teaching format that enables students to experience the whole research cycle according to Huber (2009).

2.1 Context of this study

This study was conducted at a young German research-intense university of technology that offers a variety of engineering bachelor and master degree programmes. The university aims to grow in the next years with currently ~8000 students (~1500 first year students) and ~800 academics in six departments. Most academics are involved both in teaching and research. Connecting research and teaching is highlighted in the university's mission statement of teaching and learning. Engaging students in research is therefore an important part of implementing it. There are various teaching innovations for the different stakeholders in place, such

as a qualification programme for research assistants for integrating research into teaching (see [7]), a facultative interdisciplinary project for first-year students, or an incentive programme for professors, who want to innovate learning modules or study programmes, all supported by the university's centre for teaching and learning.

2.2 Study methodology

In order to gain first insights into the views on research, teaching, engaging students in research as well as the perceived conditions at this university, data was gathered in the beginning of 2019 by six semi-structured interviews. Assuming that various stakeholders offer a valuable perspective, three different groups were surveyed, that is students, chief engineers, and professors. The position chief engineer is quite unique at the university and involves, apart from research and teaching activities, managerial functions within the respective institute. One-hour interviews were conducted with two students (S1, S2), two chief engineers (CE1, CE2) and two professors (P1, P2) that are open to teaching innovations. The sample represents a variation of gender (three female, three male persons), disciplines (process engineering; electrical engineering, computer science and mathematics; mechanical engineering; management science and technology; civil engineering), involvement in incentive innovations, activities in bachelor and/or master degree programmes, and some experience in engaging students in research. The participants were asked to:

- (1) describe their understanding of research,
- (2) define their understanding of teaching,
- (3) explain typical situations in which they engage students in research (or were engaged in research as students), and what they perceive as benefits for students and academics,
- (4) clarify what they perceive as barriers and enabling factors for implementing students' engagement in research, and
- (5) formulate recommendations or visions with regard to students' engagement in research.

Subsequently, on the basis of relevant literature ([6], [8]), a five-dimensional category system for barriers, enabling factors and ideas was designed, including 1) culture, 2) resources, 3) structures of study programmes, 4) academics' qualification and 5) students' competencies. Then, the data was analysed using thematic analysis by two researchers. Here, one researcher proceeded interviewee by interviewee while the other researcher analysed the interviews question by question.

3 RESULTS

In order to understand how the interviewees perceive barriers and enabling factors and what ideas they have on how to engage students in research, it is necessary to consider their inherent conceptions of research, teaching and students' engagement in research. Therefore, these are discussed here first. Following this, the results on perceived barriers, enabling factors and ideas are presented.

3.1 Perceptions of research and teaching

The interviewees' general conceptions of research were quite similar, varying just in certain details. The participants, except P2, all described research as a series of activities to solve a problem, to answer a question or to give an explanation, while S2 and also P2 view discovering connections as important. Following Brew's (2001) concept of research, the interviewees are mainly oriented on the product or process of research, whereas the researcher as a person with personal goals seemed to be absent from awareness in the descriptions. Further on, interviewees referred to the following central aspects: a) research as generation of new knowledge (P1, P2, CE1, S2), b) research as similar to development (CE1, CE2, S1, S2) or, on the contrary, research as system innovation vs. development as technological innovation (P1), c) difference between research at higher education institutions compared to industrial research (P1, CE2, S2), d) holistic perception of research activities within a typical cycle (P2, CE1, CE2, S2) or focus on particular activities and phases of research (P1) and e) relevance of one's own research for society (P1, CE2 and S2).

The interviewees' teaching perceptions were also quite similar in some aspects, such as the teaching approach, but vary in others. All participants, except CE2, described teaching as knowledge transmission. In addition, P1, CE1, S1, and S2 mentioned the importance of students constructing their knowledge. Moreover, all interviewees, except S2, appreciated the development of both students' professional and personal competencies as being part of teaching. Additionally, interviewees drew attention to the importance of practice in teaching (P1, P2, CE1, S1) and emphasised employability as goal of teaching (P1, P2, S1).

3.2 Perceptions of engaging students in research

When asked about their perceptions of students' engagement in research, all participants elaborated on curricular activities and, in addition, three interviewees (P1, S1, S2) described extracurricular activities. The interviewees took all students into account when talking about engaging students in research, however four participants (P1, CE2, S1, S2) additionally described forms of engagement that were only offered to selected students. All interviewees' descriptions relate to particular phases of the research process, while two interviewees (S1, CE2) take the whole research cycle into account when engaging students. Two participants (P2, CE1) stated that research done by students is of minor quality, whereas one interviewee reported on treating students on eye-level and having experience in co-publishing with students (CE2). One interviewed student expressed the feeling of being treated as research partner (S1).

The development or improvement of certain competencies was seen as a main benefit for students, including professional competencies such as solving complex or real world problems (P1, S2), understanding differences between knowledge base and generation (P2), deep-learning (CE2), understanding connections between modules (S1), understanding limitations of technology and methods (S2). As aspects of personal skills, developing self-reliance (P1, S1, S2), critical thinking (P1), interest

in research topics (CE2, S1), research skills (P2), time management, collaboration, communication and leading skills (S1) were mentioned. Furthermore, making friends with other students, getting to know institutes, and experiencing academics in their role as researchers (S1) were also indicated.

All academics highlighted that they gain joy when engaging students in research. Furthermore, advantages are the recruitment of suited students for student project work and theses (CE1, S1) or joint research projects (CE2), and building long-term networks (CE1). Additionally, S2 noted that academics can gain more empathy for students' competencies and can slip into other roles than the expert role.

The academics were asked to describe how they actively engage students in research in a typical teaching situation, whereas the students were asked to describe situations when they had been engaged in research during their studies. Interviewees' activities in engaging students in research took place mainly in three forms in the framework of Rueß et al. (2016): a) In lectures, academics present research results by describing innovative ideas (P1) or state-of-the-art-research topics (CE2); b) in brainstorming sessions in problem-based learning courses, students apply research methods (P1), simulations (CE1), programming tasks in small project works (S2), and c) students experience a research process in the framework of student projects or theses (P1, S1, CE2, P2). Interviewees' descriptions hint to individual, uncoordinated activities (P1, P2, CE1, CE2, S2) or activities that integrate students into a scholarly community (CE2, S1) according to Brew and Mantai (2017).

3.3 Perceptions of barriers, enabling factors, and ideas for improvement of engaging students in research

As a next step, the responses of the interviewees were categorized within the five-dimensional category system for barriers, enabling factors and ideas (see Chapter 2.2).

First, the cultural conditions foremost focus on strengthening the recognition of teaching. This includes more practice-orientation in engineering programmes, orientation on competence, treating students as partners as well as social engagement and industry co-operation (see *Table 1*).

Table 1. Perceptions of barriers, enabling factors and ideas for improvement of engaging students in research referring to 1) cultural aspects

#	barriers	enabling factors	ideas for improvement
1) culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the workload necessary for supervising research-based learning projects is not adequately accounted for in the teaching load (P2) • little practical work as integral part of study programmes in engineering (P1) • focus on professional rather than personal competencies and research skills (S1) • low failure tolerance (S2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • teaching recognition, e.g. by awards, funding (P2) • culture of partnering with students as co-researchers (P1, CE2) • informal meeting culture between academics and students (P1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • appreciative structure for academics' efforts in engaging students in research (P2) • teaching incentives for academics (S2) • joint problem solving projects with industry partners and communication of results, even if these question common practices (P1) • cooperative problem solving of students and academics (S1)

Second, resources named by the interviewees included efforts, staff number, infrastructure, incentives, and characteristics of projects in engineering (see *Table 2*).

Table 2. Perceptions of barriers, enabling factors and ideas for improvement of engaging students in research referring to 2) resources

#	barriers	enabling factors	ideas for improvement
2) resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • low staff number (P1, P2, CE1, S1), e.g. for coordinating teaching activities (P1, CE1) • high workload due to other competing duties (P2, CE1, S1) • high efforts, e.g. for co-working with students at pilot stands (P1), providing new topics (CE1), updating lectures (S1) • limited current resp. real data (only published resp. simulated data are available) (CE1), due to confidentiality of industrial projects (P2) • lack of informal social space (P2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • appropriate personnel at departments (P1) • investment in junior academics to supervise students projects (P2) • incentive structures, such as appropriate teaching load (P2) • staff network, e.g. for equipment loan (CE2), • more appropriate rooms and facilities, e.g. meeting places in every institute (P1), group and PC rooms (CE1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • decentralized supporting staff with pedagogical and subject competencies (P1) • funding of staff for teaching innovations and/or module coordination (CE1) • unbureaucratic process to the provision of materials for students' experimental work (CE2) • modern infrastructure, such as maker spaces (S2) • database on vacant student projects (P2)

Thirdly, structural aspects of engineering curricula were also revealed, such as the hierarchical structure of curricula, the amount of basic courses, the relation of compulsive to obligatory courses, the workload of modules as well as their coordination. Other items were the amount of practical elements, the types of inquiries and assessments, the existence or amount of given credits, the space for students' interests, courses on methods of scientific working, and the number of extracurricular activities (see *Table 3*).

Fourthly, it was found, that conditions referring to academics' qualification for engaging students in research relate first of all to their personal competencies, rather than on their professional competencies (see *Table 4*).

And last, the following conditions for engaging students in research in terms of students' attributes were addressed: students' knowledge, research skills, affective-motivational aspects, their study focus, engagement besides courses and future prospects (see *Table 5*).

Table 3. Perceptions of barriers, enabling factors and ideas for improvement of engaging students in research referring to 3) structural aspects

#	barriers	enabling factors	ideas for improvement
3) structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • uncoordinated modules (P1, CE1, S1, S2) • inappropriate credits for workload in students' projects (P1, S1) • few high quality practical work within curricula (P1, S2) • closed inquiries, complex assessment, little space in the standard curriculum, few possibilities to receive positive feedback on competencies (S1) • few choices on subjects or too many obligatory courses, too many basic knowledge courses, dominance of written exams (S2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • clustered modules with an overall research topic (P1), pedagogically coordinated courses (CE1) • integration of non-technical, uncredited courses (S1) • more practical work in problem-based learning sessions (P1) • self-dependent work in courses (CE1) • open inquiries, proper assessment, well-structured team projects in the beginning and many subject choices in master degree programmes (S2) • appropriately designed courses regarding workload, deletion of other modules, balance between basic knowledge and research integration in lectures, group projects, interdisciplinary topics (S1) • voluntary work of student groups at test stands with researchers (P1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • hierarchical, scaffolded design of curriculum that integrates research (CE1) • integration of students' projects in curricula (S1) • integration of student projects with industry partners in curricula (CE1) • support for student projects based on their own questions (S1) • enable students to specialize (P2) • smaller projects and emphasis on particular research phases in the bachelor programmes and integration of research modules in the master degree programmes (S2) • will to strengthen students' research competencies combined with product development (CE1) • addressing current societal problems (S1) • courses on methods of scientific working (CE1)

Table 4. Perceptions of barriers, enabling factors and ideas for improvement of engaging students in research referring to 4) academics' qualification

#	barriers	enabling factors	ideas for improvement
4) academics' qualification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • not enough open-minded professors with regard to modern pedagogies (S1) • professors' expert role limits their empathy for students' heterogeneous competencies and novice perspectives (S2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • open-minded, interested academics (P1, P2, CE2) • academics engage in topics of students' interest (CE2) and are open to supervise projects of students' interest (CE2, S2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • courage for offering open inquiry topics, address students' autonomy even in projects with given topics, clarify roles in a project, and motivate students to creativity and experimentation (CE2)

Table 5. Perceptions of barriers, enabling factors and ideas for improvement of engaging students in research referring to 5) students' competencies

#	barriers	enabling factors	ideas for improvement
5) students' competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • knowledge heterogeneity in the beginning of studies (S2) • uncertainty due to taking over responsibility for results, no experience in dealing with failure (S2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • students who plan a research career (CE2) • students who already know methods of scientific working (CE1) • students interested in topics and practical applications (CE1, CE2) • students with frustration tolerance, creativity, readiness for risk-taking, courage (CE2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • engagement in extracurricular activities, such as project teams (S1) • engagement in practical work at institutes (S1, S2) • active decision to select modules in the master's degree programmes with an emphasis on practice resp. research (S2)

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 Discussing perceptions of conditions for engaging students in research

Engaging students in research entails complex conditions, and these were confirmed in this study with various stakeholders at one German university of technology. Both academics and students provided pieces of a big puzzle. The findings correspond with research in other countries or disciplines. For example, room allocation, student-faculty ratio, workload, space in the curriculum, teaching efforts, teaching approaches, and mindsets as well as students' competence levels have been described as perceived barriers in the relevant literature (e.g. [6], [8]). Moreover, similar enabling factors and suggestions for engaging students in research were found, such as teaching recognition by funding, informal learning environments, open-ended inquiries, open-minded academics and perception of students' competencies (e.g. [6], [8]). In addition to that, hindering aspects found in this study were, for example, little practice as integral part in bachelor engineering programmes, the high amount of other duties for academics, many basic and obligatory courses in the bachelor programmes, closed inquiries, dominance of

written exams, knowledge transmission in lectures, and few opportunities for students to experience failure. Furthermore, positive aspects found in this study include partnering with students as co-researchers, modern infrastructures, courses in methods of scientific working, integration into the suite of non-technical courses, coordinated modules, scaffolded curriculum design and extracurricular activities, addressing students' autonomy even in given topics, and encouraging creativity. However, it is important to note that these conditions are related to some extent to characteristics of traditional engineering education in Germany (see [3]), such as in this study sample. Finally, the interviews revealed that participating academics already engage students in research, using the opportunities they have in the curriculum. However, their visions move beyond, and they suggest developing research skills in a coordinated way within the curriculum. Also, both academics and students recommend engaging in extra-curricular activities that offer teasers in research for students. Overall, the results of this study are concise with other findings with regard to the various approaches of engaging students in research (see [6]).

4.2 Discussing the methodology of this study

Thinking about the implications of the study results, some aspects have to be taken into account: This investigation follows a qualitative interview study that offered valuable additional insights in obstacles, enabling factors and recommendations for engaging students in research, perceived by qualified research assistants (see [7]). Hence, this group was excluded from this current investigation. This study focuses on a wider range of stakeholders at the university. Since following an explorative approach by conducting semi-structured interviews, the interpretation of study results underlies the known limitations of qualitative research. Furthermore, our selection of six open-minded, more experienced academics and students from one German university of technology as interview partners is limited. It has to be proved whether these results are in-line with results revealed in a questionnaire with more unexperienced stakeholders with regard to engaging students in research.

However, the study sheds some light into the interviewees' conceptions of research and teaching and the conditions of engaging students in research. While systematising conceptions on research as well as teaching in this case was cumbersome, various understandings reported (see [6]) as well as different forms of engaging students in research conceptualized (see [10]), helped to discover interviewees' perceptions and actions. Finally, described categorizations of conditions for engaging students in research (see [6], [8]) provided first insights.

In order to develop more generalizing results towards understanding barriers and enabling factors for students' engagement in research, it is required to formulate hypotheses that take into account the different perceptions of research and teaching. These should then be tested within the framework of a quantitative research design, i.e. a survey with all relevant stakeholders at more than one university from different countries.

5 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

This explorative study discussed complex conditions for implementing students' engagement in research in engineering programmes at a German university of technology. It is argued that when interviewing relevant stakeholders about conditions, their background perceptions are important as well. Some of the revealed barriers, enabling factors, and recommendations have been reported in the existing literature and some of the new findings seem to be connected to some extent to traditional engineering education in Germany. The results suggest that some individuals desire activities for engaging students in research such as coordinated skill development, i.e. at the level of module clusters or over the whole curriculum. Also, they demand extracurricular activities on an individual level. This study requires a follow-up, i.e. deriving hypotheses and quantitative surveying of all stakeholders. As a next step, it is recommended to include widely recognized multi-level key strategies and their appropriate application and further development, involving all stakeholders. Such strategies have a high potential to foster the development of engineering talents for industry 4.0.

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